

20 November 2020

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4274720

State Environmental Policy in the Context of Environmental Management

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Abstract. The article analyses the shift dynamics of the leading paradigms of the political predicates at different stages of social development. Addressing to the real world and the roots that go back to tradition makes it possible to recognize a new paradigm, which the 21st century is interested in viz. the paradigm of environmental protection. To develop a long-term policy of creating an environmental management system, it is crucial to determine the stages of its implementation in close connection with the socio-economic development. It is believed that at the first stage, in economic turmoil, when there is a recession and a shortage of basic necessities, “do no harm” should be the underlying principle of the environmental policy. It is important at least to stop further destruction of natural complexes. The second stage should be devoted to the implementation of nature management and nature restoration projects. The third stage should cover the period of post-crisis recovery and sustainable development, consisting in the restoration of the natural environment or ecological reconstruction. Characterizing different types of environmental policy (such as managerial, pluralistic and collective) makes it possible to justify the expedience of such a model, which is based on environmental legislation and institutionalism. However, this model requires a certain level of development of civil society and its individual institutes. Analyzing the practice of solving environmental problems by the world community shows that environmental legislation is increasingly interfering in politics. And not only in the form of prohibitions, restrictions, sanctions and exemptions, but also as a basis for ensuring viable, environmentally safe, sustainable development.

The world has been undergoing fundamental changes in politics over the past twenty years. Pragmatism and extensive nature management are getting supplemented by the principles of harmonization of human-environment relations as well as the search for a strategy of sustainable development of the society and the biosphere. Ecology is becoming an area of political interests and decisions, whereas politics is beginning to take greater

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account of environmental factors. Even such a field of activity as environmental policy has been singled out. This necessitates the substantiation at the modern scientific level of the principles aimed at overcoming the current situation as well as forming an environmental policy so that Ukraine could implement environmentally sound development.

According to the analysis, it was the political and the socio-economic factors that determined reduction of the negative anthropogenic effect on Ukraine's natural environment. The political and legal mechanism of developing environmental security of the country is, on the one hand, the interaction between different branches of government, and on the other – the activity of civil society itself. Violation of the basic principles of environmental culture on the plane of this interaction often leads to significant deformation in achieving the goal.

Creating a system of environmental security suggests meeting the environmental requirements of society and it should be given priority over some aspects of traditional national security. In the conditions of Ukraine's independent nation-state development, it has become objectively possible to reduce the negative anthropogenic effect on the natural environment by forming the foundations and implementing a modern National Environmental Policy based not only on high technology, but also on universal priorities.

The study of environmental policy as a new line of public policy, its essence, principles, priorities for social regulation of national development was to some extent conducted in the works by F. Kanak, M. Kyselyov and M. Khylyko [1, 2]. Today, moral and political paradigm shift is happening fast and is clearly felt. Those beliefs that were considered sincere until recently, have now lost their former unambiguity. During the global economic crisis, some political trends are showing off their true non-conservationist colours. Profits prove to be more important. It is already obvious that modern post-industrial societies can no longer develop in the traditional way, there is a collapse of real institutions in society and this poses a great threat to environmental security.

It is now obvious that economy is the dominant subsystem and the central sphere of the present-day culture. However, V. Hösle points out that it has not always been like this [3]. For example, the relationship between economics and politics in ancient times was completely different from today. Political decisions in an ancient polis hardly affected the economy, finances or social policy, while modern states are primarily concerned with addressing these issues. The ancient state was less responsible for its citizens in the economic sphere than the modern state. Nevertheless, if the economy is not necessarily the centre of a culture, then what other area will be central?

In today's world, the national limitations of politics have not yet been fully surmounted. Global economic policy is yet to come, although there are coordinated national economic policies. In national politics, the economy has been playing an increasingly important role, especially since the liberal law-based state became a social welfare state. This transformation is put into practice within the same paradigm.

Modern states pursue an unprecedented exploitative foreign policy in order to meet the economic requirements of their citizens and, thus, to maintain their own social world. If the needs of the inhabitants of the nation state begin to grow spontaneously, the state must meet these needs, but it can only do so where there is the least resistance. There are, in fact, two sides, two types of the objects. On the one hand, there is nature, on the other hand – nations that have not yet developed the principle of the rule of law. These are, for example, semi-feudal states, in short, the "third world" peoples, where they try to stop exploitation by law. Nature in the legal philosophy of the modern age has always been deprived of civil rights. The national socialist system of modern politics, captivated by the economic paradigm, will undoubtedly lead the Earth to an ecological calamity, and the "third world" countries will be in the most miserable condition.

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The ecological crisis as well as the economic one is forcing us to reject the national-economic paradigm in politics. The right policy is the one that can maintain the natural bases of our environment to the fullest extent. By no means should it promote maximum quantitative economic growth by encouraging the satisfaction of any, even absurd, needs. Nor should it seek cultural and linguistic unity of the nation to the detriment of others. Finally, it is not a policy that seeks to forcibly achieve religious homogeneity. Thus, the economic paradigm will soon have to give way to the ecological one. According to V. Höfle, the 21st century will be the century of environmental protection [3].

Hopefully, the ecological crisis will eventually be seen as a common enemy of humanity, which can only be surmounted by joint efforts. However, it is possible that in the near future the environmental problem will lead to new contradictions, when foreign policy will be focused on what everyone is ready to do for the sake of the environment. "Friend-enemy" relations retain their significance not only by international contacts, but also within the country or even any individual institute. Within the country, they may become aggravated in connection with the nature of foreign policy. Limited progress in understanding the advantages of the new paradigm may lead to even sharper contrasts at the most traditional political poles, for example, between the powers adhering to the old paradigm and those seeking ecological transformation of the industrial society.

It is a well-known opinion that when paradigms shift, the meaning of classical political predicates also changes. A person who seeks to contribute to the normative goal is referred to as "progressive". The one who wants to return to the old goal is considered "retrograde". According to the economic paradigm of thinking, he who seeks to increase the consumption level is believed to be progressive. With the advent of the environmental paradigm, such behaviour under certain conditions is reactionary as it harms the environmental health status. In the absence of a reliable criterion for determining the paradigms, opponents can sincerely accuse each other of being "retrograde".

Yet, no matter how alarming the future may seem, critical analysis of the origin and formation of the ecological idea can give one the strength needed to develop a new paradigm, even if it is now outlined only in general. Knowledge of the real world helps to get rid of the disadvantages of the time, saving them from death in the whirlpool of their own subjectivity. The past gives man such knowledge. Without roots going back to tradition, it is impossible to create the future. Such an appeal is certainly valuable as an aspiration to find the hidden spiritual treasures in order to create a new paradigm which is of interest to the century of environmental protection.

Ecological crisis is a crisis of the current mechanisms of social adaptation in the social and natural environment, primarily due to the passivity of thinking and loss of ability for self-regulation. It is necessary to change the direction of this interaction through the reform of social institutions and management.

To develop a long-term policy of creating an environmental security in Ukraine, it is crucial to determine the stages of its implementation in close connection with the socio-economic development. At the first stage, in economic turmoil, when there is a recession and a shortage of basic necessities, "do no harm" should be the underlying principle of environmental policy.

It is important at least to stop further destruction of natural complexes. The second stage should be devoted to the implementation of nature management and nature restoration projects. One of the crucial directions is the creation and application of new environmentally friendly technologies.

The third stage should cover the period of post-crisis recovery and sustainable development, consisting in the restoration of the natural environment or ecological reconstruction.

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The peculiarity of Ukraine's environmental security policy is currently determined not only by the scale of problems that arise, but also by the specific character of their solution under difficult socioeconomic conditions. Businesses are trying to maximize profits through maintaining the competitive capacity of their products by reducing costs, even environmental ones. In this case, easily accessible resources are used, often in predatory ways.

The primary and the most complicated problem of Ukraine's environmental security policy is the creation of an economic mechanism for its implementation. Classical political economy was based on the principle that the market has to cope with all problems without any interference. However, the 20th century made fundamental amendments to the situation. The concept of state regulation of the economy, put forward and developed by J. Keynes, F. Roosevelt and J. Soros, showed the seriousness of the idea of the forecasted economy [4]. J. Soros calls the doctrine of non-interference of the state in the economy "market fundamentalism". He also warns that today it is a greater danger to the world community than totalitarian ideology. However, nowadays we need to care for more things, e.g. for managing not only the economy but also the entire historical process and for the scientific forecast of social development. The imperative of our technological civilization is the principle of responsibility for life, which is constantly endangered and can come abruptly to an end. For the first time in human history, human activity may lead to irreversible consequences and cause irreparable damage to both human life and the environment. Hence emerges the idea of responsibility for the future. The principle of responsibility turns us directly to the realm of politics, to the sphere of human community management [5].

The problem of responsibility becomes especially topical for another reason. An important result of the development of technological civilization is the globalization of the consequences of government decisions, which can lead (and they sometimes really do) to the irreversibility of social processes and nonrenewal of vital natural resources. In critical conditions, the state assumes the burden of responsibility. However, this reduces the degree of independence of individual citizens. Realising that the civil society and the state need to act purposefully, it is very important to measure the state influence, otherwise society is threatened with either totalitarianism, inevitable stagnation and degradation, or chaos viz. senseless waste of spiritual and physical strength of the nation, inability to overcome the crisis and, as a result, also stagnation and degradation.

In the conditions of the general ecological crisis, it is, first of all, necessary to develop a new system of requirements, which would limit one or another system of human activity. All branches of government are obliged to effectively interfere in production activities and in the economic process, while the ideological code of the industrial society was based on non-interference. Politics in general, and hence the environmental policy, presupposes the existence of their own subjects. Due to their participation and activity it is carried out according to the underlying principles and using appropriate methods.

The state is increasingly interfering and is more and more often recognized as a subject of environmental policy, but there is no agreement on whether it should perform its function in a centralized or decentralized way. It is difficult to give an unambiguous answer to this question, because environmental problems are revealed at different levels, although they are always interdependent and global. Thus, the question arises: How can individual states be subjects of their own environmental policy without a global, international environmental policy? Therefore, just as the destiny of the Earth cannot be entrusted to several individual states, the solution to environmental problems should also be global.

How exactly the state will implement its environmental policy depends on its internal, on the nature of the economy and many other factors.

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In the late 1980s, the process of ecologization of public consciousness became more intensive. The ecological activity of the population increased dramatically. The green parties appeared and mass public ecological movements gained strength. Various political parties include conservation in their election platforms.

It is already clear that almost all socio-economic and political structures on the planet will somehow deal with the environmental affair in the coming decades. That is why one more feature should be added to the list of numerous characteristics of a “civilized” state, namely: a social and democratic state governed by the rule of law should also become ecological. Otherwise, it is doomed because it will not be able to guarantee its citizens’ rights (and especially the rights of future generations) to live in a healthy natural environment. It is quite logical that the rights of future generations and the nature are being realized with a certain delay, because there is no sovereign and conscious legal entity. After all, according to V. Höhle, ignoring these rights signifies a threat to the conditions of people’s real survival, and, consequently, any state whether law-based or not [3]. Parties and political movements that misunderstand and therefore underestimate the role of ecology and do not see the latest trends in the movement of world civilization to a new ecological state, risk disappearing from the political scene. That is why, it should be expected that political parties and movements will form their own environmental structures and bodies, which will play a crucial role in political activity. This is confirmed by the fact that there are now distinct processes of environmental politicization and political environmentalization.

The policy of creating a national and regional environmentally sound management system provides for the following priorities:

- problem analysis of ecological and ecological-economic situation in the country and region;
- selection of priorities for development, elaboration and approval of national environmental policy taking into consideration regional peculiarities;
- elaboration of the long-term state strategic program of ecological and economic development;
- formation of the organizational structure and the management bodies of ecological and economic development.

The uncertainty of many modern conditions hinders the full implementation of these tasks. Even at the initial stage of the movement towards eco-development, much remains unclear. There are no fully fledged inventories of natural resources; the system of national environmental standards and regulations is not complete; it is unknown what price the population is ready to pay to achieve environmental development goals (especially in economic turmoil) and, finally, to what extent the existing system of government and management is able to embrace the idea of eco-development or make decisions on its implementation. The level of uncertainty is increasing due to the lack of an advanced monitoring system in the country, a single information system, without which it is impossible to reach the required modern level of operational management.

Thus, the national environmental policy should be a key document in the elaboration of a strategic program of environmental and economic development. The transition from the destructive technocratic paradigm to the concept of environmentally friendly development requires appropriate basic conditions. 1) A carefully developed unified state environmental policy, supported by a long-term strategic program. 2) Developed legislation in the field of nature management and environmental protection. 3) Sufficient financial and material support. 4) Participation of the population in the process of elaborating and making decisions on the crucial practical tasks of ecological development. 5) Scientific and methodological, informational and normative security of local ecological-economic programs. 6) A balanced personnel policy, according to which access to power and

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environmental management are determined by professionalism and competence. 7) International cooperation and support.

All these conditions are quite important, but what is crucial is the competence of the power structures. First and foremost, it should be noted that the entire nature management system is in urgent need of qualified specialists, susceptible to the new requirements of environmental and economic policy and able to fully neutralize the environmental illiteracy of government officials and business managers.

Building an environmentally safe state in Ukraine requires the elaboration of ways to optimally manage the current environmental situation at three levels *vz.* scientific and theoretical, socio-technological, political and practical, on the basis of highly developed environmental culture.

The article offers the concept of reasonable human dominance over the nature. It rests on the analysis of formation of philosophical and ideological bases of optimal scientific, theoretical and sociotechnological management of the current environmental situation. The content of the concept can be defined in the following theses.

1) The crisis in the current environmental situation in Ukraine is caused, for example, by technical and technological activities, the guidelines of which were formed in the 20th century on the grounds of philosophical and ideological principles of industrial culture. Within this system, the transforming activity of man was qualified as the one through which the world had to maximise the comfort of human life.

2) Building their relationship with nature based on the priority of their own needs, man of the information-oriented industrial society exercises their power over nature. The peculiarities of the culture in the industrial society do not allow the formation of philosophical and ideological principles of a harmonious relationship between man and nature. Reasonable power over nature is nothing more than overcoming the aggressive attitude to it.

3) It is only possible to search for optimal forms of environmental safety management and ways out of the current environmental situation in Ukraine by taking into account the historical and cultural tradition of the attitude of Ukrainian ethnic group to nature. Nature should be included in the domain of moral categories.

4) Taking into consideration the historical and cultural tradition, it is necessary to significantly increase the role of the state in overcoming the environmental crisis in Ukraine. State management of the environmental situation should be clearly defined and comprehensive, given the serious condition of the environment. Insufficiently strict environmental actions of the state and power structures may lead to an ecological calamity, even against the background of high activity of public organizations.

5) Scientific and theoretical management of the relationship between man and nature within the existing global socio-ecosystem requires a new understanding of the concept of management (compared with the management of socio-economic or natural systems). The underlying principles of this understanding are based on the idea of co-evolutionary development of man and nature.

6) The failure of the social goal, which is the improvement of the current environmental situation in Ukraine, is caused by a significant discrepancy between the “upper” (philosophical and scientific-theoretical) and “lower” (political and practical) of project levels to design the optimal environmental situation.

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Conclusion

Thus, effective environmental policy is designed to overcome managerial fragmentation and should be based on long-term strategic thinking as well as the high professionalism among politicians.

The dynamics of the leading paradigms of thinking in society showed the following. The economic paradigm emphasises the importance of the human consumption level. Ecological paradigm is the paradigm of environmental protection.

The article determines the stages of the implementation of long-term policy of ecological safety development in Ukraine in close connection with socio-economic development. At the first stage, in economic turmoil, when there is a recession and a shortage of basic necessities, “do no harm” should be the underlying principle of environmental policy. The second stage should be devoted to the implementation of nature management and nature restoration projects. The third stage should cover the period of post-crisis recovery and sustainable development, consisting in the restoration of the natural environment or ecological reconstruction.

Characterizing different types of environmental policy (such as managerial, pluralistic and collective) makes it possible to justify the expedience of such a model, which is based on environmental legislation and institutionalism.

Analyzing the practice of solving environmental problems by the world community shows that environmental legislation is increasingly interfering in politics. And not only in the form of prohibitions, restrictions, sanctions and exemptions, but also as a basis for ensuring viable, environmentally safe, sustainable development.

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